

Mars Rover API

- Develop an API that moves a rover around on a grid.
- You are given the initial starting point (x,y) of a rover and the direction (N,S,E,W) it is facing.
- The rover receives a character array of commands.
- Implement commands that move the rover forward/backward (f,b).
- Implement commands that turn the rover left/right (l,r).
- Implement wrapping from one edge of the grid to another. (planets are spheres after all)
- Implement obstacle detection before each move to a new square. If a given sequence of commands encounters an obstacle, the rover moves up to the last possible point and reports the obstacle.
- Example: The rover is on a 100x100 grid at location (0, 0) and facing NORTH. The rover is given the commands "ffrff" and should end up at (2, 2)